

Morita-Baylis-Hillman reaction of benzaldehydes with methyl vinyl ketone at ambient temperature using cross-linked poly-4-vinylpyridine as a solid heterogeneous base catalyst in the presence of hydrogen peroxide[†]

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Abstract : Morita-Baylis-Hillman (MBH) reaction of various aromatic aldehydes and methyl vinyl ketone (MVK) is effectively catalyzed by cross-linked poly-4-vinylpyridine (CPVP), a solid heterogeneous polymer-based base catalyst, in the presence of hydrogen peroxide in an aqueous *tert*-BuOH medium at ambient temperature. The reaction in DMF gives a mixture of MBH adduct and the adduct of the reaction of MBH adduct with MVK. The reaction in aqueous *tert*-butanol gives selectively the MBH adduct in high yield and the catalyst is recyclable. This is the first report of the use of this combination of a solid polymeric base (CPVP) with hydrogen peroxide as a catalyst for MBH reaction.

Keywords : α -Methylene- β -hydroxy compounds, cross-linked poly-4-vinylpyridine, Morita-Baylis-Hillman reaction.

Introduction

Over the recent years synthetic organic chemistry is remodeled to meet the requirement of atom economy, selectivity, fast kinetics, and in general the requirements of green chemistry. The newer methods of synthesis developed to meet these goals involve polymers as reagents and as heterogeneous catalysts. The polymeric framework may be used as the supports in some cases¹. Many polymer-based acid catalysts have been developed, though polymer-based basic catalysts are limited. The reusability of such catalysts makes them ecofriendly. In similar context, solvent-free reactions are most effective for carrying out green synthesis. The use of water as a solvent has been developed to make synthesis green².

The Morita-Baylis-Hillman (MBH) reaction is one of the most important C-C bond forming reactions in organic synthesis. Due to its many advantages, like atom economy, nonmetal catalysis, mild conditions and compatibility with multiple functional groups, it has drawn considerable attention in the past decade³. The reaction has a great synthetic potential as it provides highly

functionalized products which can be used for building more complex structures from relatively simple starting compounds⁴⁻⁶. The classical version of the reaction involves reaction of activated olefins, such as α,β -unsaturated ketones, nitriles and acrylates, with aldehydes, ketones and aldimines in the presence of a basic nucleophilic catalyst. The common catalysts are DABCO⁷, DMAP⁸, DBU⁹, phosphines¹⁰, chalcogen species¹¹ and imidazole¹². Recently, Namboothiri has extended the scope of the reaction by synthesizing substituted α -hydroxyalkylated nitroalkenes by the reaction of activated carbonyl compounds, like ethyl glyoxylate, pyruvic aldehyde, trifluoromethyl pyruvate and diethyl ketomalonate, with various aromatic, heteroaromatic and conjugated nitroalkenes using DMAP and imidazole catalysts¹³. Under special conditions the reaction can be extended to alkyl halides as the electrophilic reagents¹⁴.

Though MBH reaction is a common C-C bond forming reaction, it is quite sluggish and has some limitations. The reaction of phenyl vinyl ketone with benzaldehyde is not limited to the monoadduct, and the initial BH adduct reacts further with a second molecule of phenyl vinyl

[†]In honour of Professor Sunil Kumar Talapatra on the occasion of his 80th birthday.

Table 1. MBH reaction of 4-nitrobenzaldehyde with MVK in different solvents and in the presence of different PVP-based catalysts and H₂O₂

Entry	Catalyst	Temp. (°C)	Solvent	Time (h)	Product (%)	
					3a	4a
1	PVP	27	Dioxane	72	No reaction	
2	PVP	27	MeOH	72	No reaction	
3	PVP	27	DMF	72	No reaction	
4	PVP-SiO ₂	27	DMF	72	No reaction	
5	PVP	0 ^a	DMF	48	40	20
6	PVP-Mg-Al HT	0 ^a	DEE	24	43	31
7	PVP-SiO ₂	0 ^a	DEE	48	20	-
8	PVP-SiO ₂	0 ^a	DMF	48	No reaction	
9	CPVP-3	27	DMF	72	No reaction	
10	CPVP-3	0 ^a	DMF	48	40	20
*11	PVP	30	DMF	6	10	40
*12	CPVP-3	30	DMF	6	10	40

Reaction conditions : 4-Nitrobenzaldehyde (3 mmol), MVK (3 mmol), catalyst (3 mmol), H₂O₂ 30% w/v (mole equi. of pyridine in catalyst), *sonicated reaction; ^atemperature at which enone, catalyst, and hydrogen peroxide mixed, reaction carried out at 27 °C.

would be generated *in situ* and the reaction catalyzed by the same. The reaction using only PVP was ineffective in DMF, dioxane and methanol. Similarly, CPVP and supported PVP catalyst also were ineffective.

MBH reaction is temperature-sensitive and sometimes the reaction which does not take place at or above room temperature may take place at a lower temperature. In this reaction the mode of addition of the reactants was very crucial. It was necessary to mix the enone, base and hydrogen peroxide at 0 °C; the addition of aldehyde may be carried out at 0 °C or at 27 °C. PVP catalyzed the reaction at this temperature in DMF and an important observation was that a mixture of two products (by GC-MS) MBH product **3a** (R=H) and **4a** was formed. Corma has reported adduct **4a**, formed by the Michael type of addition or MBH product with MVK²², along with the normal MBH product. The product mixture also contains a small amount of 4-nitrobenzoic acid and unreacted aldehyde.

Among the CPVP catalysts, CPVP-1 and CPVP-2 were poor as they swell in organic solvents, hence the stirring of the solution was difficult, and separation of the catalyst and product difficult. CPVP-5 and CPVP-7, though

did not swell and separated easily from the reaction mixture, showed poor activity, probably due to higher networking and less *N*-oxide formation. CPVP-3 was the best catalyst for the reaction and could be easily separated after the reaction by filtration. The polymer beads of CPVP-3 maintain their integrity in DMF, the polymer did not swell, and the compound could be easily filtered. The reaction gave the same mixture of **3a** and **4a**. Hence for further work, CPVP-3 was used.

The reaction was also attempted in the presence of ultrasound. We have earlier determined cavitation intensities of various solvents and DMF was found to have 39% cavitation intensity as compared to water²². Since DMF is a good solvent for the reaction, the sonochemical reaction was carried out in DMF using an ultrasound cleaning bath. Under these conditions, the reaction was found to be very fast and in the product mixture, the adduct **4a** was the major product.

The next task was to achieve selectivity towards the MBH product. In the MBH reaction, solvent plays a crucial role and in this context water is very important. Hu showed that the MBH reaction of methyl acrylate and acrylamide was accelerated simply by conducting the reaction in aqueous dioxane solution²³. Recently, Aggarwal showed that when Yb(OTf)₃ was used, further acceleration of the reaction was achieved in water²⁴. Cheng showed remarkable acceleration of imidazole-promoted MBH reaction in aqueous basic solution using a base like Na₂CO₃, NaHCO₃, NaH₂PO₄-Na₂HPO₄^{25,26}. DeSouza evaluated aqueous organic solvent combinations for the reaction using DABCO catalyst, mainly comprising DMSO/water, DMF/water, *tert*-BuOH : H₂O, and MeCN/water and noted that the solvent system depended on the reactants, e.g. for acrylonitrile, *tert*-butanol/water (60 : 40) and for methyl acrylate; DMSO/water (60 : 40)²⁷. The role of water has been explained by Harvey²⁸. In conclusion, various workers found water in combination with the other solvent as a tunable factor for this reaction³¹.

These reported studies encouraged us to try *tert*-butanol as a solvent. In *tert*-butanol alone about 45% of yield of the MBH product **3a** was obtained (Entry 11, Table 2). Combination of *tert*-BuOH-H₂O was promising with respect to the yield and selectivity of the MBH adduct (Table 2). In this system, surprisingly, only MBH product was obtained in all the cases. *tert*-BuOH : H₂O (v/v) in 40 : 60 ratio gave 80% yield of **3a** in 24 h (Entry

Table 2. The reaction of 4-nitrobenzaldehyde and MVK in *tert*-BuOH-H₂O mixture

Entry	<i>tert</i> -BuOH : H ₂ O (v/v)	Yield of 3a (%)
1	0 : 100	59
2	10 : 90	30
3	20 : 80	35
4	30 : 70	54
5	40 : 60	80
6	50 : 50	70
7	60 : 40	50
8	70 : 30	55
9	80 : 20	50
10	90 : 10	50
11	100 : 00	45

Reaction conditions : 4-Nitrobenzaldehyde (3 mmol), MVK (9 mmol), H₂O₂ 30% w/v (3 mmol), CPVP-3 (100 wt% of 4-nitrobenzaldehyde); solvent (12 mL), temp. 30 °C, time 24 h.

Table 3. The reaction of 4-nitrobenzaldehyde and MVK in the presence of different quantity of CPVP-3

Entry	Amt. of cat. (mass % of aldehyde)	Yield of 3a (%)
1	40	10
2	50	20
3	60	35
4	70	54
5	80	60
6	90	67
7	100	80
8	110	82
9	120	83

Reaction conditions : 4-Nitrobenzaldehyde (3 mmol), MVK (9 mmol), H₂O₂ 30% w/v (mole equi. of pyridine in catalyst), *tert*-BuOH + H₂O (4.8 mL + 7.2 mL), temp. 30 °C, time 24 h.

5, Table 2). For further study we used *tert*-BuOH : H₂O (v/v; 40 : 60) as the solvent.

The amount of catalyst was varied to change the mol % of pyridine in the catalyst (Table 3). 100 mass% of CPVP

gave 80% yield of 3a.

In order to find out the optimum ratio of aldehyde to MVK, the reaction was carried out using different mole ratios of aldehyde to MVK (Table 4). The best mole ratio of aldehyde : MVK was 1 : 3.

Scheme 2. Plausible mechanism of the MBH reaction.

Table 4. The reaction of 4-nitrobenzaldehyde and MVK with different mole ratios of aldehyde to MVK

Entry	Aldehyde : MVK mole ratio	Yield of 3a (%)
1	1 : 1	40
2	1 : 1.5	50
3	1 : 2	65
4	1 : 2.5	70
5	1 : 3	80
6	1 : 3.5	80
7	1 : 4	80

Reaction conditions : 4-Nitrobenzaldehyde (3 mmol), H₂O₂, 30% w/v (3 mmol), CPVP-3 (100 wt% of 4-nitrobenzaldehyde); *tert*-BuOH + H₂O (4.8 mL + 7.2 mL), temp. 30 °C, time 24 h.

A plausible mechanism of the reaction is given in Scheme 2.

CPVP-3 is a heterogeneous basic catalyst and could be easily separated from the reaction mixture by simple filtration and could be reused. The recovered catalyst could be used for successive three runs without any decrease in the yield of the product (Table 5).

Under the optimized conditions, various substituted

Table 5. Reusability of CPVP in the reaction of 4-nitrobenzaldehyde and MVK

Run	Time (h)	Yield of 3a ^a (%)
1	24	80
2	24	80
3	24	78

Reaction conditions : 4-Nitrobenzaldehyde (3 mmol), MVK (9 mmol), *tert*-BuOH : H₂O (4.8 mL : 7.2 mL), CPVP = 0.5 g (100 wt% of aldehyde), Temp. 33 °C. ^aIsolated yield.

aromatic aldehydes were reacted with MVK to obtain the corresponding α -methylene- β -hydroxy compounds (Table 6). It was observed that the yield of the product was significantly governed by the type of substituent in the aldehyde. Electron-withdrawing group was favourable, while electron-donating group unfavorable. The reaction of 4-nitrobenzaldehyde with acrylonitrile, methyl acrylate and cyclohex-2-en-1-one failed.

Conclusion

MBH reaction of aromatic aldehydes with MVK is effectively catalyzed by PVP cross-linked with 1,4-DVB

Table 6. The Baylis-Hillman reaction of aromatic aldehydes with MVK in the presence of CPVP-3

Entry	Aldehyde	Active olefin	Product (3a-3m)	Time (h)	Yield (%)
1		24	80		
2		24	78		
3		24	75		
4		24	78		

Table-6 (contd.)

5		24	75		
6		24	73		
7		24	65		
8		24	58		
9		24	60		
10		24	50		
11		24	60		
12		6 days	20		
13		6 days	10		

Reaction conditions : Aromatic aldehyde (3 mmol), MVK (9 mmol), H₂O₂ 30% w/v (3 mmol), CPVP-3 (100 wt% of aromatic aldehyde); *tert*-BuOH + H₂O (4.8 mL+ 7.2 mL; 40 : 60), temp. 30 °C.

Isolated yield.

*100% selectivity of product was observed in all cases.

(3%) (catalyst CPVP-3) and hydrogen peroxide. The role of hydrogen peroxide appears to be conversion of PVP into its *N*-oxide. The reaction selectively gives MBH prod-

uct. The catalyst is reusable. This is the first report of the use of this combination of a solid polymeric base (CPVP) with hydrogen peroxide as a catalyst for MBH reaction.

The reaction takes place at ambient temperature and was very sensitive with respect to solvent. A mixed solvent system *tert*-butanol-water (40 : 60, v/v) is most effective. The presence of water makes the solvent system very effective.

Experimental

Silica was procured from M/s Spectrochem Pvt. Ltd., Mumbai, particle size ~230–400 mesh, pH 6.5–7.5 (10% aq. solution). 4-Vinylpyridine was polymerized in carbon tetrachloride under nitrogen in the presence of AIBN to obtain PVP²⁹. CPVP was prepared by radical suspension polymerization of 4-VP and 1,4-DVB, using water as a solvent, toluene as a porogen, AIBN as an initiator, and PVA as a stabilizer²². Using 1, 2, 3, 5 and 7 wt% of DVB, catalysts CPVP-1, CPVP-2, CPVP-3, CPVP-5 and CPVP-7, respectively, were prepared. Mg-Al hydrotalcite (Mg/Al = 3) was prepared by the reported procedure³⁰.

Preparation of supported catalyst : To a solution PVP (0.5 g) in methanol (20 ml), support material (5 g) was added portion wise with constant stirring. The resulting slurry was stirred for 2 h at r.t. and methanol was removed under reduced pressure at r.t. to obtain a free-flowing catalyst. PVP was supported on silica and Mg-Al hydrotalcite (Mg/Al = 3) to obtain catalysts PVP-SiO₂ and PVP-Mg-Al HT, respectively.

Typical MBH reaction procedure

To a stirred solution of CPVP-3 (100 mass% of aldehyde), H₂O₂ 30% w/v (mole equiv. of pyridine from CPVP-3) in *tert*-BuOH : H₂O (40 : 60 v/v, 4.8 mL + 7.2 mL) at 0 °C, MVK (9 mmol) was added and the reaction mixture stirred for about 15 min at the same temperature. The solution was brought to r.t. and aldehyde (3 mmol) was added. The solution was stirred at r.t. (30 °C) and monitored by TLC. After optimum time, the catalyst was filtered and washed with ethyl acetate (2 × 5 mL). The filtrate was extracted with ethyl acetate (3 × 10 mL). The ethyl acetate layer was dried over anhydrous Na₂SO₄ and concentrated under reduced pressure to obtain the product. The product was purified by column chromatography on silica gel and using pet ether : ethyl acetate (80 : 20; v/v).

All compounds were obtained as thick oily liquids with pale yellow colour.

Spectral data :

3-[1-Hydroxy-1-(4-nitrophenyl)methyl]-3-buten-2-one (3a)^{31-33,35} :

FT-IR (neat) : 3467 (-OH), 2963, 1726 (C=O), 1521, 1380 (NO₂) cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (CDCl₃, TMS, 300 MHz) : δ 2.36 (3H, s, COCH₃), 3.50 (1H, br, OH), 5.67 (1H, s, CHOH), 6.04 (1H, s, C=CH₂), 6.27 (1H, s, C=CH₂), 7.55 (2H, d, *J* 9.0 Hz, ArH), 8.19 (2H, d, *J* 9.0 Hz, ArH) ppm; MS (EI, 70 eV) : *m/z* 221 (M⁺), 144, 134, 116, 77.

3-[1-Hydroxy-1-(2-nitrophenyl)methyl]-3-buten-2-one (3b)^{32,35} :

FT-IR (neat) : 3460 (-OH), 3000, 1722 (C=O), 1526, 1378 (-NO₂) cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (CDCl₃, TMS, 300 MHz) : δ 2.37 (3H, s, COCH₃), 3.53 (1H, br, OH), 5.79 (1H, s, CHOH), 6.16 (1H, s, -C=CH₂), 6.20 (1H, s, C=CH₂), 7.46 (1H, m, ArH), 7.65 (1H, m, ArH), 7.77 (1H, dd, *J* 7.8, 1.5 Hz, ArH), 7.96 (1H, dd, *J* 8.3, 1.5 Hz, ArH) ppm; MS (EI, 70 eV) : *m/z* 161, 144, 134, 116, 104, 77.

3-[1-Hydroxy-1-(3-nitrophenyl)methyl]-3-buten-2-one (3c)^{32,35} :

FT-IR (neat) : 3468 (OH), 3000, 1741 (C=O), 1521, 1374 (NO₂) cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (CDCl₃, TMS, 300 MHz) : δ 2.34 (3H, s, COCH₃), 3.61 (1H, br, OH), 5.66 (1H, s, CHOH), 6.18 (1H, s, C=CH₂), 6.36 (1H, s, C=CH₂), 7.43 (1H, dd, *J* 9.0, 9.0 Hz, ArH), 7.70 (1H, d, *J* 8.4, ArH), 8.12 (1H, d, *J* 8.4 Hz, ArH), 8.21 (1H, s, ArH) ppm; MS (EI, 70 eV) : *m/z* 220 (M⁺-1), 204, 174, 162, 131, 115, 105, 77.

3-[1-Hydroxy-1-(4-chloro-3-nitrophenyl)methyl]-3-buten-2-one (3d) :

FT-IR (neat) : 3465 (OH), 3000, 1741 (C=O), 1531, 1374 (-NO₂), 786 (C-Cl) cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (CDCl₃, TMS, 300 MHz) : δ 2.31 (3H, s, -COCH₃), 3.67 (1H, brs, -OH), 5.58 (1H, s, CHOH), 6.11 (1H, s, C=CH₂), 6.26 (1H, s, C=CH₂), 7.26–7.77 (2H, m, ArH), 7.83–7.84 (1H, m, ArH) ppm; MS (EI, 70 eV) : *m/z* 254 (M⁺-1), 238, 208, 165, 139, 115, 70.

3-[1-Hydroxy-1-(4-cyanophenyl)methyl]-3-buten-2-one (3e)³⁴ :

FT-IR (neat) : 3465 (OH), 3000, 2283 (CN), 1741 (C=O), 1445 (ArC=C) cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (CDCl₃, TMS, 300 MHz) : δ 2.31 (3H, s, COCH₃), 3.51 (1H, br, OH),

5.61 (1H, s, CHO), 6.04 (1H, s, -C=CH₂), 6.23 (1H, s, C=CH₂), 7.45 (2H, d, *J* 8.1 Hz, ArH), 7.55 (2H, d, *J* 8.4 Hz, ArH) ppm; MS (EI, 70 eV) : *m/z* 200 (M⁺-1), 186, 140, 130, 115, 77.

3-[1-Hydroxy-1-(4-fluorophenyl)methyl]-3-buten-2-one (3f)³⁴ :

FT-IR (neat) : 3465 (OH), 3000, 1741 (C=O), 1440 (ArC=C) cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (CDCl₃, TMS, 300 MHz) : δ 2.32 (3H, s, COCH₃), 3.35 (1H, br, OH), 5.58 (1H, s, CHO), 5.99 (1H, s, C=CH₂), 6.18 (1H, s, C=CH₂), 6.98–7.07 (2H, m, ArH), 7.27–7.50 (2H, m, ArH) ppm; MS (EI, 70 eV) : *m/z* 193 (M⁺-1), 179, 147, 133, 123, 97.

3-[1-Hydroxy-1-(4-chlorophenyl)methyl]-3-buten-2-one (3g)^{31,33,35} :

FT-IR (neat) : 3465 (OH), 3000, 1741 (C=O), 1448 (ArC=C) cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (CDCl₃, TMS, 300 MHz) : δ 2.32 (3H, s, COCH₃), 3.53 (1H, br, OH), 5.55 (1H, s, CHO), 6.01 (1H, s, C=CH₂), 6.17 (1H, s, C=CH₂), 7.24 (2H, d, *J* 9.0 Hz, ArH), 7.27 (2H, d, *J* 9.0 Hz, ArH) ppm; MS (EI, 70 eV) : *m/z* 211, 209 (M⁺-1), 197, 195, 175, 157, 141, 139, 115, 113, 77.

3-[1-Hydroxy-1-(2-chlorophenyl)methyl]-3-buten-2-one (3h)³⁶ :

FT-IR (neat) : 3471 (OH), 3000, 1741 (C=O), 1448 (ArC=C) cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (CDCl₃, TMS, 300 MHz) : δ 2.40 (3H, s, COCH₃), 3.49 (1H, br, OH), 5.68 (1H, s, CHO), 6.00 (1H, s, C=CH₂), 6.17 (1H, s, C=CH₂), 7.24–7.59 (4H, m, ArH) ppm; MS (EI, 70 eV) : *m/z* 211, 209 (M⁺-1), 175, 157, 141, 139, 115, 113, 105, 103, 77.

3-[1-Hydroxy-1-(3-chlorophenyl)methyl]-3-buten-2-one (3i)³⁷ :

FT-IR (neat) : 3377, 3467 (OH), 3000, 1738 (C=O), 1448 (ArC=C) cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (CDCl₃, TMS, 300 MHz) : δ 2.28 (3H, s, COCH₃), 3.65 (1H, br, -OH), 5.52 (1H, s, CHO), 6.00 (1H, s, C=CH₂), 6.18 (1H, s, C=CH₂), 7.20 (3H, m, ArH), 7.31 (1H, s, ArH) ppm; MS (EI, 70 eV) : *m/z* 211, 209 (M⁺-1), 197, 195, 175, 141, 139, 115, 113, 77.

3-[1-Hydroxy-1-(2-bromophenyl)methyl]-3-buten-2-one (3j)³⁸ :

FT-IR (neat) : 3450 (-OH), 3000, 1742 (C=O), 1447

(ArC=C) cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (CDCl₃, TMS, 300 MHz) : δ 2.27 (3H, s, COCH₃), 3.76 (1H, br, OH), 5.54 (1H, s, CHO), 6.04 (1H, s, C=CH₂), 6.21 (1H, s, C=CH₂), 7.20–7.28 (4H, m, ArH) ppm; MS (EI, 70 eV) : *m/z* 255, 253 (M⁺+1), 185, 175, 157, 132, 115, 77.

3-[1-Hydroxy-1-(3-bromophenyl)methyl]-3-buten-2-one (3k)³⁷ :

FT-IR (neat) : 3461 (-OH), 3000, 1738 (C=O), 1447 (ArC=C) cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (CDCl₃, TMS, 300 MHz) : δ 2.33 (3H, s, COCH₃), 3.30 (1H, br, OH), 5.44 (1H, d, CHO), 6.00 (1H, d, *J* 1.0 Hz, C=CH₂), 6.21 (1H, s, C=CH₂), 7.19 (1H, t, 7.8 Hz), 7.27 (1H, d, *J* 7.7 Hz, ArH), 7.38 (1H, dt, *J* 7.8, 1.4 Hz, ArH), 7.49 (1H, t, 1.7 Hz, ArH) ppm; MS (EI, 70 eV) : *m/z* 255, 253 (M⁺+1), 175, 129, 115, 77.

3-[1-Hydroxy-1-phenylmethyl]-3-buten-2-one (3l)^{33,35} :

FT-IR (neat) : 3430 (OH), 3026, 1734 (C=O), 1443 (ArC=C) cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (CDCl₃, TMS, 300 MHz) : δ 2.30 (3H, s, COCH₃), 3.73 (1H, br, OH), 5.62 (1H, s, CHO), 5.99 (1H, s, C=CH₂), 6.16 (1H, s, C=CH₂), 7.20–7.37 (5H, m, ArH) ppm; MS (EI, 70 eV) : *m/z* 175 (M⁺-1), 161, 107, 77.

3-[1-Hydroxy-1-(4-methoxyphenyl)methyl]-3-buten-2-one (3m)^{31,35} :

FT-IR (neat) : 3425 (OH), 3015, 1732 (C=O), 1441 (ArC=C) cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (CDCl₃, TMS, 300 MHz) : δ 2.34 (3H, s, COCH₃), 3.79 (3H, s, OCH₃), 5.58 (1H, s, CHO), 5.72 (1H, br, OH), 6.06 (1H, s, C=CH₂), 6.24 (1H, s, C=CH₂), 6.86 (2H, d, *J* 9.0 Hz, ArH), 7.26 (2H, d, *J* 9.0 Hz, ArH); MS (EI, 70 eV) : 208 (M⁺), 205, 191, 175, 157, 145, 137, 108, 94, 77, 43.

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